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trans4num Newsletter #1

This is the first issue of **trans4num** Newsletter! Within these pages you will find news and information about the project activities. We invite you to navigate on our website and find out more about **trans4num**! Make sure you follow us on social media too.

In this newsletter we introduce you to the project, the partners and the NBS sites, while also sharing first project materials and upcoming events.

Enjoy the read!

About the project

trans4num is a four-year project funded under the Zero Pollution call as an EU-China international cooperation action on nature-based solutions (NBS) for nutrient management in agriculture.

trans4num's ambition is to broadly enhance the NBS implementation in Europe with an integrative and tested multi-level approach, in dialogue with academic partners, practice partners and societal stakeholders.

With a total of six work packages (WPs) **trans4num** will work to understand NBS, concepts and approaches (WP1), explore innovative NBS in regions of intensive farming (WP2), monitor and optimise NBS related nutrient flows (WP3), assess NBS effects in a SET context (WP4) and to scaling up and out project results (WP5).

[Read more about trans4num](#)

trans4num consortium

The **trans4num consortium** brings together 14 partners from Europe and 9 partners from China in a well-balanced transdisciplinary team with complementary expertise ranging from biophysical-agronomic (WU, AU, FiBL, RRes) to socio-economic disciplines (FiBL, SZE, AU, RRes).

trans4num has a **strong multi-actor approach**, bringing together a comprehensive suite of actors including demonstration farms, farmer organisations (SPNA), NGOs (P4All, PKE) and SMEs (PMA, CO, HCC).

[EU partners](#)

trans4num objectives

trans4num's main objective is to develop and test innovative NBS practices and pathways that contribute to a socio-ecological transformation of existing intensive agriculture systems towards increasingly sustainable nutrient management.

In particular, trans4num will: **develop** a disaggregated **understanding** of NBS potentials for achieving sustainable agricultural practices, **understand and analyse** the complex interdependencies of applying NBS, **develop** a dynamic,

smart **nutrient management tool** to support decision making for optimal nutrient supply and will **asses** the (net) **impact** of technological and social innovations, as well as policies related to NBS.

[Read more](#)

trans4num NBS sites

trans4num has selected four European and three Chinese sites. Different NBS innovations will be studied and tested on each site using a multi-actor systems approach designed to define, monitor, and assess the effects of each innovation at the field, farm, landscape and regional levels.

The main innovations studied on the four **European NBS** sites are:

- crop rotation and bio based fertilisers in **Hungary**
- legumes, strip-cropping and agro-forestry in **The Netherlands**
- biomass crops and crop rotation in **Denmark**
- crop rotation, biomass crops and farmyard manure in **The United Kingdom**

[Check out the EU NBS sites](#)

trans4num library

[NBS overview](#)

[Deliverables](#)

[Communication](#)

Future Events

CALL FOR CHALLENGES

trans4num
**INSPIRE
HACKATHON
2024**

Call for challenges open! The hackathon is a unique opportunity to contribute to the development of impactful solutions, work with like-minded individuals from around the world, and benefit from the knowledge and experience of seasoned mentors.

[Learn more](#)

JOINT STAKEHOLDER CONFERENCE

trans4num, ECONUTRI & PestNu Joint Stakeholder Conference:

Nature-based solutions for sustainable nutrient management in agriculture towards eliminating soil, water and air pollution by nitrogen and phosphorus emissions

[Learn more](#)

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

DEC 2022 - MAR 2024

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